

‘Terrorist Recruiters’ Versus ‘Terrorist Slayers’: Weaponizing Syria in Russian Information Warfare

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Abstract: This article focuses on Russian information warfare in the context of the Syrian civil war. From the beginning of its military intervention, Russia justified its presence in Syria by claiming to fight “international terrorism.” This article draws on corpus linguistic analyses to examine this claim by analyzing the linguistic anatomy of Russian information warfare on Twitter. Findings reveal how recurring linguistic patterns construct information tactics that condemn the United States as a “terrorist recruiter” and “civilian killer” and praise Russia as a “terrorist slayer” and a “humanitarian.” We compare these findings to open-source conflict data to discuss how these information tactics were related to kinetic maneuvers on the ground.

Keywords: Disinformation; information warfare; strategic communication; corpus linguistics; Russia; terrorism.

Introduction

Four years into the Syrian civil war, by the summer of 2014, the Islamic State (ISIS), a violent Salafist terrorist group, conquered large areas of northern and eastern Syria and Iraq, declaring an Islamic caliphate in the region. ISIS’ rise was rapid and unexpected, and the Syrian government’s violent and lethal crackdown on the opposition spiraled out of control. After Syrian President Bashar al-Assad allegedly made a formal request for Russian military assistance, Russia entered the Syrian civil war on September 30, 2015, as a major player and supporter of the Assad regime and its allies.¹ These allies included Hezbollah, Iranian Quds and Revolutionary Guard Forces, allied-foreign Shi’a militias, and local Syrian forces operating in rebel-held territory. In parallel to the Russian military intervention, a Russian state-sponsored disinformation campaign was spreading on Twitter, calling on the US and other Western governments to join the Russian-Syrian “anti-terrorist front” against ISIS. Despite international outcry and condemnation of the human rights abuses Syrians suffered at the hands of their government, Russia continued to defend the Assad regime by arguing that compared to ISIS, Assad was a lesser of two evils.² It portrayed Assad’s campaign as a legitimate war on jihadi terrorism, which served to justify Russia’s military intervention.³

To divert attention from the Assad regime’s human rights violations and war crimes, Russian state media also portrayed the 2011 Arab Spring as a US/Western scheme against Russia: a geopolitical operation “to plant puppet regimes in the attacked countries,” which “ended in failure.”⁴ In order to better understand their information warfare (hereafter IW), it is essential that our analytical framework rests upon a firm understanding of the ways in which Russia operationalizes language to achieve strategic objectives. Drawing on a corpus linguistic methodology, this article will examine claims made by Russian Twitter

accounts that the aim of Russia's involvement in the Syrian civil war was mainly to fight "international terrorism." Specifically, this article will analyze the linguistic anatomy of Russian IW, focusing particularly on unpacking the narrative signature with which Russia seeks to influence perceptions and advance strategic objectives.

This article is organized as follows. The article begins by introducing key concepts and provides an overview of research on Russian disinformation campaigns. It then introduces the methodological framework and describes the data. The analysis section illustrates in detail how Russian information tactics are built up through recurring linguistic patterns that condemn the US as a "terrorist recruiter" and "civilian killer" and praise Russia as a "terrorist slayer" and a "humanitarian." The following section discusses the implications of how such analyses can improve our ability to identify information tactics within Russian IW and interpret their strategic intentions. The paper concludes by discussing how the information tactics identified in Russia's disinformation campaign were related to kinetic maneuvers, i.e., actual events on the ground.

Literature Review: Russian Information Warfare

Key Terminology and Definitions

Before reviewing existing research on Russian disinformation campaigns, it is important to first introduce some key concepts relevant to the study of IW. The internet and social media have contributed significantly to the weaponization of information by the fast-paced dissemination of misinformation and disinformation, propaganda and conspiracy theories.⁵ Even though digital media helps amplify the spread of disinformation, it is worth pointing out that "it is only where the underlying institutional and political-cultural fabric is frayed that technology can exacerbate existing problems and dynamics to the point of crisis."⁶ Given the sheer volume, volatility and velocity of information in the global information environment aided by technology, machine learning, and algorithms, the study of IW is fundamentally a pursuit in social cybersecurity, as its targets are not IT systems, but "humans and the society that binds them."⁷

The terms *propaganda*, *information warfare*, and *disinformation* are especially relevant for this paper as they are related to the idea of manipulative use of information. Propaganda has been defined as a type of communicative tactic whose purpose is to intentionally provoke an emotional response from a target audience rather than to merely disseminate information.⁸ Propaganda research has shown that controlling a narrative that dominates public discussion has the power to manipulate the attitudes and beliefs of target audiences.⁹ An important distinction between propaganda and IW is that propaganda typically targets the local population while IW is aimed at foreign adversaries with the purpose of sowing confusion, fear, and distrust among the population of "enemy" states.¹⁰ While there are several working definitions of IW developed for a range of political, academic, government, and military contexts, overall, it is understood as the use of "information as a weapon" and the dissemination of propaganda in order to gain an information advantage

over an adversary.¹¹ Most recently, IW has also been defined as “a strategy for the use and management of information to pursue a competitive advantage, including both offensive and defensive operations.”¹²

Propaganda and IW operations characteristically involve the coordinated dissemination of disinformation. Disinformation is distinguished from misinformation on the basis of intent: misinformation can be defined as the unintentional spread of incorrect, misleading, and false information; in contrast, disinformation is spread intentionally and systematically in order to deceive and manipulate the opinions and behavior of target audiences, from the general public to foreign governments.¹³ This paper draws on the 2018 definition of the High Level Expert Group on Fake News and Online Disinformation of the European Commission: “Disinformation [...] includes all forms of false, inaccurate, or misleading information designed, presented and promoted to intentionally cause public harm or for profit.”¹⁴ This definition is useful because it highlights the intentionally deceptive and manipulative nature of disinformation. Another relevant concept, *strategic narrative*, is defined as “a compelling story,” whose aim is to create shared meanings that “shape the behavior of domestic and international actors.”¹⁵ This master “story” contains smaller stories that all become embedded in a larger *master narrative*.¹⁶ For example, a *master narrative* portraying Russia as a more ethical and capable global partner than the US may encompass a diversity of embedded *strategic narratives* emphasizing Russia’s military might and humanitarian motives.

Russian Disinformation Campaigns

Disinformation campaigns are not new phenomena: the term itself can be traced back to the Russian word дезинформация (*dezinformatsiya*) coined during the Cold War.¹⁷ In its more recent 2011 *Draft Convention on International Information Security*, Russia describes disinformation as “manipulation of the flow of information in the information space of other governments, disinformation or the concealment of information with the goal of adversely affecting the psychological or spiritual state of society, or eroding traditional cultural, moral, ethical, and aesthetic values.”¹⁸ Indeed, Russia’s weaponization of information makes full use of the social diffusion of information, treating it as both the medium and the subject of conflict in IW.¹⁹

While the study of propaganda has long interested researchers, scholarly interest in information warfare has increased significantly since the annexation of Crimea by Russia in 2014, and it surged after Russia’s interference in the 2016 US elections.²⁰ The US intelligence community has since concluded that Russian intentions were to undermine liberal democracy by sowing distrust in the democratic process—an objective requiring the dissemination of numerous conflicting narratives to resonate with mutually exclusive political ideologies.²¹ It has been well established that this objective was carried out by a Russian state-sponsored “troll factory,” the Internet Research Agency (IRA), which operated thousands of troll accounts on social media in order to influence the 2016 US

elections.²² During the 2016 US elections, these troll accounts experimented with *trading up the chain*, i.e., planting a story, hoax, or conspiracy theory on a blog or news outlet with low reporting standards, which is then picked up and circulated by mainstream outlets, and amplified by automated social media accounts.²³ In this manner, disinformation can reach a mass audience several degrees removed from its source, making its message appear more organic and rendering attribution back to Russian intelligence all the more difficult. During the 2020 US elections, security officials were primarily concerned with so-called "perception hacks," or the coordinated attempt to create the perception that voting processes were compromised, while inflicting little to no real damage to election infrastructure.²⁴ In this type of campaign, the intention is not to manipulate the physical voting systems and processes (i.e., altering votes and tallies), but rather to manipulate the psychology of the American voter and their faith in free and fair elections to the point of crisis.

To realize an information environment where objective reality cannot exist, and where any single narrative is as valid as the next, Russian IW employs what Keir Giles calls an "elastic targeting of different audiences with different implausible and mutually contradictory narratives."²⁵ This carnival mirror's representation of world events enables Russia to physically fight the realities they create, such as intervening to "protect" allegedly oppressed Russian speakers in Georgia in 2008, Crimea in 2014, the separatists republics of Lugansk and Donetsk in 2022, and fighting against international terrorism in Syria beginning in 2015.²⁶ The multifaceted nature of this "digital blitzkrieg" muddles and delays analysis and response-time such that Russian objectives can be secured before international consensus can be reached as to what actually occurred and what should be done about it.²⁷

Russia operates in a perpetual state of information war.²⁸ While tactics may differ between operations targeting Russia's "near abroad" in the former Soviet Union and those in its global "far abroad," Kremlin IW generally seeks to advance three overarching objectives: re-establishing the Russian sphere of influence, damaging the influence of the West, and projecting Russia's position as a global superpower.²⁹ The delivery of information under the Russian IW masthead has been described as a "firehose:" high-volume and multichannel; rapid, continuous, and repetitive; and, perhaps above all else, lacking commitment to objective reality and consistency.³⁰ Giles observes that "even if disinformation is not successfully inserted into the policy-making chain, and only spreads in mass and social media, the effect can be to create a permissive public opinion environment where Russian narratives are presented as factual."³¹ Further, the Atlantic Council identified four major moves in Russian disinformation: *dismissing* the critic, *distorting* the facts, *distracting* from the main issue, and/or *dismaying* the audience, which became widely known as the 4D framework.³² While the 4D framework introduces mostly negative information tactics, this article will show that Russian IW does not exclusively rely on negative rhetoric to manipulate the narrative. Since disinformation campaigns are thought to provoke an emotional response in their target audience, this article will analyze the linguistic anatomy of Russian IW on the microblogging site Twitter in the context of the Syrian civil war, focusing specifically on claims about fighting "international terrorism."

Research Method: Corpus Linguistic Analyses

The overall research questions guiding this study are the following: 1) how did Russia frame its own involvement in the Syrian civil war, and 2) how did Russia portray the international coalition's involvement, led by the US, in Syria? To answer these questions, this article draws on two sets of data. The first comprises a corpus of publicly available English-language Russian Twitter accounts between 2016 and 2020. The second dataset draws on open-source conflict data of Russian military activity in the Syrian civil war. To examine disinformation tactics, we draw on the methodology of corpus linguistics, which enables both automated quantitative and qualitative analyses of recurring linguistic patterns in their context.³³ Since Russia has claimed that its involvement in the Syrian civil war was mainly to fight “international terrorism,” we will use the results of analyses from both sets of data to discuss how kinetic maneuvers, i.e., actual events on the ground, were related to the information tactics identified in Russia's disinformation campaign.

The tweets analyzed in this paper are part of a large dataset included in Twitter's Information Operations Archive.³⁴ As this article focuses specifically on Russian information warfare, we have narrowed down the dataset analyzed for this article to include English-language tweets only. The finalized dataset was collected from 100 Twitter accounts, which have since been identified as state-linked accounts and deleted by Twitter. In contrast with tweets sourced from overt, publicly attributed Kremlin sources (e.g., @KremlinRussia), the accounts we analyze can be considered part of a covert operation, because they are unattributed to the Russian state, pretending instead to be local citizens and journalists, among other false identities. The dataset comprises a total of 51,594 tweets, 2,473 of which are retweets, and 1,841,553 words including hashtags (Table 1); it was pre-processed and cleaned using the Tidyverse package in RStudio, an open-source software for data science.³⁵ After preparing the data for processing and analysis, it was loaded into the corpus linguistic program, Sketch Engine, which was used to store and analyze the dataset.³⁶

The open-source conflict data was recorded between 2017 and 2020. It was accessed from the data export tool of the Armed Conflict Event and Location Data Project, a non-profit organization receiving funding from international government agencies including the US Department of State, the Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and the German Federal Foreign Office.³⁷ The data consists of actors involved in a conflict event (perpetrators as well as those affected), the location of that event, the number of fatalities, the type of event (e.g., battles, violence against civilians, explosions/remote violence, riots, protests, and strategic developments), and the date the event occurred.

Table 1. Breakdown of data by number of tweets, sentences, words

TOTAL # TWEETS	51,594
Total # sentences	56,130
#Word Types	79605
#Word Tokens (cleaned; stop list)	680,600
Total # words	1,841,553

Our methodology comprised three analytical steps: we performed word frequency, keyword, and concordance analyses. Specifically, corpus linguistic quantitative analyses focused on word frequency and keyword analyses, while the concordancer function of Sketch Engine allowed closer qualitative analysis of wild card searches based on frequency and keyness. For example, as exemplified by Table 2, the wild card search for *kill**, indicated by the asterisk, has returned 1,526 hits including word forms such as *kill*, *killing*, and *killer*. To perform qualitative text analyses, analysts can then click on the search term, also termed as Key Word in Context (KWIC), in each concordance line in order to examine their usage in their textual context. Sketch Engine allows displaying KWICs in two formats: as one line of text with the KWIC in the middle of the concordance line, or as a complete sentence, with longer sentences displayed as multiple lines. While a one-line concordance line is visually more elegant, in this paper we chose to illustrate some examples as full sentences in order to display complete tweets and thus better understand their full context.

Table 2. Five randomly selected concordance lines for *kill**

#	Left context	Keyword in context	Right context
1	air strikes, 5 civilians were	Killed	#Syria #US
2	More than 50 terrorists	Killed	, more than 20 captured
3	in the western city of #Aleppo,	Killing	one person and injuring four
4	#MSU fighters and civilians were	Killed	and more than #400 people
5	the shelling of pro-Turkish	Killers	from the SNA(TFSA)

Key Themes Related to the Syrian Civil War

The starting point for corpus linguistic analyses is typically running a word frequency analysis.³⁸ Word frequency analyses are concerned with the number of occurrences (i.e., hits) of words or word forms ordered from the most to the least frequent item. The results in Table 3 show the top ten most frequent content words found across the entire dataset, after loading a list of stop words into Sketch Engine (i.e., after excluding highly frequent grammatical words such as articles and prepositions, e.g., *the*, *of*, etc.). The middle column of the table shows *absolute* frequency, that is, words actually occurring in the corpus. The third column shows *relative* frequency, that is, the occurrence of a particular word per

million words.³⁹ The most frequent word across the entire dataset is the modal verb *will* with 3,990 hits, which occurs ~1,051 times in every one million words. The other words can be broadly grouped into semantic categories of geopolitical entities (e.g., *US, Syria, Russia*) and non-specific groups of people (e.g., *people, militants, terrorists, civilians*).

Table 3. Top 10 words in the corpus

Word	Frequency	Freq. per Million
1. will	3,990	1,051.43
2. people	3,911	1,030.61
3. US	3,659	964.21
4. militants	2,163	569.99
5. Syrian	1,717	452.46
6. Russian	1,541	406.08
7. Syria	1,531	403.44
8. terrorists	1,435	378.15
9. Russia	1,214	319.91
10. civilians	879	231.63

Keyword analyses are concerned with words and expressions that are characteristic of a kind of discourse.⁴⁰ Keywords typically occur with *unusual frequency*; in other words, they are statistically significantly *overused* in the focus corpus (i.e., the data set compiled for this study) by comparison with a reference corpus (emphasis added).⁴¹ The reference corpus used in this study was the English Web 2020 (enTenTen20), available by default in Sketch Engine. It consists of 38 billion words excluding poor quality content and spam.⁴² When keywords are grouped semantically, they can reveal overall recurring patterns of usage.⁴³ Table 4 shows the top 50 words identified as keywords in the corpus. Based on their keyness, the following semantic categories of interest can be identified: lexical items related to the Syrian civil war, specifically its locations (e.g., *Idlib, Aleppo, Hama, Raqqa*) and the language of war (e.g., *destroy, attack, kill, airstrikes, shelling, etc.*) (cf. Lukin); US-allied forces (e.g., *NATO, UN, CIA*); terrorists and terrorist organizations (e.g., *militant, terrorist, ISIS*); the Russian military (e.g., *forces, military, liberation*); those impacted by the civil war (e.g., *civilians, refugees*); and Russian humanitarian action (e.g., *humanitarian, aid, convoy*).⁴⁴

Table 4. Top 50 keywords in the corpus (Reference corpus: English Web 2020 (enTenTen20))

1. idlib	11. sdf	21. raqqa	31. military	41. arms
2. tahrir	12. turkish	22. armed	32. liberation	42. cia
3. militant	13. humanitarian	23. turkey	33. un	43. destroy
4. syrian	14. civilian	24. refugee	34. threats	44. radical
5. saa	15. isis	25. russian	35. terrorism	45. attack
6. aleppo	16. convoy	26. russia	36. airstrikes	46. kill
7. erdogan	17. ceasefire	27. nato	37. russians	47. army
8. syria	18. putin	28. shelling	38. explosion	48. fighting
9. terrorist	19. checkpoint	29. forces	39. bomb	49. war
10. hama	20. daesh	30. missile	40. crisis	50. terror

After identifying semantic categories of interest based on keyword analyses, we have manually examined the word frequency list in order to identify further synonyms and names of and references to semantic categories specifically that construe the collectivized entities *The USA* and *Russia* (inclusive of some instances of human collectives; cf. Halliday and Matthiessen) as well as the human collectives *terrorists* and *civilians*.⁴⁵ The synonyms indicative of these four main collectives identified across the dataset are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Collectivized entities and human collectives: USA, Russia, terrorists, civilians

Collectivized entities	
USA	Russia
The United States	Russia
The #UnitedStates	#Russia
the US in Syria	The #Russian Federation
The #US	#Russian air defense systems
the US Air Force	The Russian military
The international coalition led by the #United-States	#Russian military
the western coalition led by the United States	#RussianNavy
The US-led coalition	Russian Air Force
#UnitedStates	Russian #AirForce
#USA	Russian Aerospace Forces
#AmeriKKKa	
#FourthReich	
Human collectives	
The #Americans	The #Russians
US military instructors	#Russian #military_men
#American instructors	Russian military medics
#US intelligence agencies	Russian nurses
	#Russian experts
	#Russian soldiers

Human collectives	
Terrorists	Civilians
militants	the Syrian population
terrorists	Syrian civilians
#militants	Syrian citizens
#terrorists	Syrians
#jihadists	civilians
Insurgents	refugees
terrorist gangs	people
#terrorist groups	#Muslims
#militants of various armed formations	Arabs
pro-US insurgents groups	women
#USAterrorists	children
NATO backed jihadis	displaced persons
illegal armed groups	local residents
Jabhat al-Nusra	families
ISIS	inhabitants
#ISIL	
Daesh	
ISIS terrorists	
#ISIS #terrorists	
#ISIS_snipers	
#ISIS' "sleeper cell"	
#AlNusra militants	
Dzhebbat al-Nusra radicals	
HTS (Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham) militants	
Jabhat Tahrir Surya militants	
soldiers of Tahrir al-Sham	
Feylaq al-Rahman snipers	
Jaish al-Islam fighters	
New Syrian Army militants	
the terrorist organisation Tahrir al-Sham	
the terrorist alliance Tahrir al-Sham	
enemies	

For follow-up qualitative analyses tweet sampling was based on the results of the corpus linguistic keyness and word frequency analyses. We treated the four collectives introduced above as *node* words, i.e., pre-selected vocabulary items (see Hunston for a detailed introduction), to generate concordance lines.⁴⁶ As an illustrative example, Table 6 shows a random selection of five concordance lines for the word *militants*.

Table 6. Five randomly selected concordance lines for militants

#	Left context	Keyword in context	Right context
1	The #Americans continue training	militants	of illegal armed groups.
2	US military instructors continue training	militants	on the territory of the military base in El #Tanf
3	The #UnitedStates has regained its title as the main recruiter of	militants	for Syria's southeastern factions.
4	the #Americans recruit the ranks of the	#militants	under their control in the #AtTanf zone
5	#US intelligence agencies continue to train	#militants	in the Al-Tanf camp

Given their high frequency and keyness, we processed the entire dataset focusing more closely on five node words included within the human collectives: *militants*, *terrorists*, *people*, *civilians* and *refugees*. We ran wildcard searches for each of these words (e.g., **militant**): the asterisk signals a wildcard for one or more characters, so these searches retrieved all instances that include hashtags as well as singular and plural forms of these nouns. A preliminary reading of the resulting concordance lines revealed that the *United States* and *Russia*, which also appear in the list of the most frequent words, are often mentioned in tweets containing these wildcard searches.

In order to narrow down the search to a specific context, concordance lines can be selected by using the filter option in Sketch Engine, also known as “advanced context word function.”⁴⁷ As we show in Table 4, there are several synonyms of and references to both the US and Russia across the dataset. For example, mentions of the US include *The USA*, *America*, *#Americans*, or *the international coalition led by the United States*. Similarly, synonyms and references to Russia include, for example, *the Russian Federation*, *Russians*, or *#Russian*. For each node word search, we uploaded a list of all mentions of the US and Russia identified in the randomized sample, to keep lines containing only the node word **militant** in the context of Russia, for example. The advanced context word function allows searching not only for one word or expression but also a list of lexical variations or synonyms of the search term. The results presented below account for such lexical variation.

The human collectives *militants* and *terrorists* appear as the fourth and eighth most frequent words (Table 3) and their singular forms appear in the list of 50 keywords (Table 4). A wild card search for **militant** and **terrorist** returned 3,330 and 3,626 hits respectively. The asterisk stands for extra characters: it allows us to retrieve search terms preceded by hashtags as well as different word forms, i.e., singular and plural forms of these nouns. We then filtered the context of the tweets containing **militant** by searching for references to the *United States*, which retrieved 1,049 hits, and in the context of **terrorist**, 1,143 hits. Filtering the context by searching for references to *Russia* returned 1,301 and 1,253 hits respectively.

We then ran the same search on the other statistically significant human collectives *people*, *civilians*, and *refugees*. With 3,911 hits, Table 3 above lists *people* as the second most frequent word in the entire dataset. A wild card search for **people* returned a total of 4,298 concordance lines; filtering its context by searching for both the *United States* and *Russia* returned 969 and 1,005 concordance lines respectively. With 879 hits, Table 3 above shows *civilians* as the tenth most frequent word. A wild card search for **civilian** retrieved a total of 1,286 concordance lines; filtering its context by searching for the *United States* and *Russia* returned 388 and 421 hits respectively. Since the keyword *refugee* is ranked 24th, we included it in our analyses: a wild card search for **refugee** returned a total of 1,173 concordance lines; filtering its context by searching for the *United States* and *Russia* retrieved 485 and 536 hits respectively. Performing these searches using the advanced context word function retrieved 4,034 concordance lines for the *United States* and 4,516 for *Russia*, a combined total of 8,550 concordance lines (Table 7a). Table 7b presents illustrative examples of each of the collectives filtered for context.

Table 7a. Concordance lines of key human collectives filtered for context

Keyword	Hits	Freq per M	Filter US	Freq per M	Filter Russia	Freq per M
*people	4,298	1,132.59	969	255.35	1,005	264.83
terrorist	3,626	955.51	1,143	301.2	1,253	330.19
militant	3,330	877.51	1,049	290.66	1,301	342.84
civilian	1,286	338.88	388	102.24	421	110.94
refugee	1,173	309.1	485	127.81	536	141.24
Total #	13,713		4,034		4,516	
Total combined # of concordance lines in sub-corpus: 8,550						

Table 7b. Illustrative examples of key human collectives filtered for context

Keyword	Filter: US	Filter: Russia
militant	The #ISIS militants , with the support of the United States and the Kurds, freely cross the Euphrates River, heading for the south-western regions of the Syrian province of #DeirezZor.	The militants reportedly want to launch an offensive in the coming days, using tanks and heavy equipment. #Syria #HTS Only Russia can de-escalate.
terrorist	The United States is not able to fight terrorists , and there is no particular desire.	In the event of the start of a military operation against terrorists in Idlib, Russia will be ready to greatly increase the number of military aircraft in Syria for the quickest possible destruction of terrorists.
*people	The United States is behind the terrorist attack in Ahwaz. On Saturday, September 22, a terrorist attack took place in Ahwaz, Iran, where 25-29 people were killed.	Russia does not tire of helping the friendly people of Syria.
civilian	The United States launched a series of air strikes on the homes of Syrian citizens in Hadjin, which resulted in regular civilian casualties.	Russia and Syria do not violate provisions of international humanitarian law as there are no actions targeting civilians or civilian infrastructure.
refugee	the # UnitedStates is not interested in solving the problems of Syrian refugees .	The # Russian # military escorted a convoy of 800 refugees returning to the liberated En-Naim.

After identifying the key semantic categories that construe the collectivized entities and the human collectives presented above, we aimed to unpack the online “chatter” surrounding the topics of militants/terrorists and people/civilians/refugees: What did the Russian Twitter accounts say about these human collectives when related to the US and Russia? In the following concordance analyses we present how the US is portrayed in an exclusively negative light as an immoral actor and Russia in an entirely positive light as both a capable and moral actor representing military might and a moral high ground in the fight against international terrorism.

Concordance Analyses: Key Information Tactics in Russian Information Warfare

In this section we analyze what kinds of messages accumulate in Russia's disinformation campaign, specifically about fighting international terrorism in Syria to understand how they cluster into information tactics that praise Russia's involvement in Syria and condemn that of the US. Following Tilakaratna and Szenes, and Szenes, we use the term *cluster* to mean recurring patterns of the same type of linguistic resources.⁴⁸ As shown in Table 7a, by filtering the context of key node words, we created a sub-corpus made up of a total of 8,550 concordance lines. We then used the random sampler function of the concordancer to create a representative sample of 200 tweets, which formed the basis for our qualitative analyses. For reasons of space, we will limit our presentation to five randomly selected tweets per cluster.

Information Tactic 1: America the Terrorist Recruiter

For the concordance analysis we first searched for the keywords **militant** and **terrorist** in order to examine how these human collectives are positioned within the sub-corpus and what key messages about them emerge. First, we focus on the concordance lines containing **militant** and **terrorist** filtered for the context of the *United States*. As highlighted in Table 8, we found that they occur together with different forms of the verbs *train* or *recruit* in each of the tweets analyzed. It is important to note here that these verbs do not convey any positive or negative valence on their own. However, together with the verb *continue* they function to invoke and thus amplify Russia's condemnation of the US for the training and recruiting of terrorists as they portray the action of terrorist training as ongoing and long-lasting. We have named this cluster "*America the terrorist recruiter*" and it constructs the first information tactic identified in Russian IW against US involvement in the Syrian civil war.

Table 8. Cluster 1: "the US + RECRUITS / TRAINS + militants / terrorists"

#	Left context	Keyword in context	Right context
1	The #UnitedStates has regained its title as the main recruiter of	#militants	for Syria's southeastern factions.
2	the #Americans recruit the ranks of the	militants	under their control in the #AtTanf zone
3	The United States continues to train	terrorists	at its military base in the #AlTanf
4	#American instructors train	#terrorist	groups from the #NewSyrianArmy
5	#US intelligence agencies continue to train	militants	i# n the Al-Tanf camp

Information Tactic 2: America the Civilian Killer

When filtering the concordance lines containing **civilian** for the context of the *United States*, we found that the verb *kill* occurs most frequently in the concordance lines retrieved across the data. Coupled with quantifying the civilians killed by the US (e.g., *dozens of thousands of, more than 300, more than 10000*) as well as specifying locations (e.g., *in #Syria, in #Raqqa city*), piling up such tweets functions to amplify Russia’s condemnation of the US relative to both number of casualties and also spread (cf. Hood).⁴⁹ As in the first information tactic, where Russia accuses the US of training and recruiting terrorists in Syria, it also blames the US and the international coalition for killing civilians. Illustrated by Table 9, we named this cluster realizing the second information tactic identified in Russian IW “*America the civilian killer.*”

Table 9. Cluster 2: “the US + KILLED + x number of + civilians”

#	Left context	Keyword in context	Right context
1	The #US killed dozens of thousands of	civilians	in #Syria
2	The US-led coalition killed hundreds [sic]	civilians	at eastern #Euphrates
3	The US Air Force killed 30	civilians	, the majority of the dead - women and children
4	The US in Syria killed more than 10000	civilians	in the city of Raqqah
5	The international coalition led by the #UnitedStates killed only	civilians	#Syria #BreakingNews

In both information tactics presented above the same type of linguistic resources are repeated: the *United States continues training/recruiting* terrorists and *killed* civilians. The linguistic resource of repetition has an intensifying effect in discourse (cf. Hood); thus, posting (and retweeting) tweets that repeat the same message help 1) reinforce Russia’s accusations against and 2) amplify Russia’s condemnation of the US.⁵⁰ We will now show how Russia shifts its negative information tactics portraying the US as “terrorist recruiter” and “civilian killer” to positive information tactics that praise Russia’s involvement in Syria.

Information Tactic 3: Russia the Terrorist Slayer

Here we focus on the randomized selection of concordance lines that contain the node words **militant** and **terrorist** filtered for the context of *Russia*. The verbs *destroy* and *kill* were identified as frequently occurring in these tweets. As opposed to the negative information tactic that portrays the US as terrorist recruiters, the positive information tactic in Table 10 below represents Russian military might and its defense capabilities, amplified

by references to amount, space, and intensification (e.g., *dozens of militants, in the Jarjanaz area, successfully destroyed*). As mentioned above, quantification and repetition both serve to amplify Russia’s condemnation of the US as part of the Russian IW toolbox. Another strategy for amplification is “infused intensification,” i.e., upscaling the degree of intensity of the meaning of lexical items: through the choice of the verb *destroy*, compared to *kill*, Russia steps up the amplification of Russian military capability and exaggerates its image as a successful geopolitical power in eliminating terrorists and fighting against international terrorism.⁵¹ We will name this pattern “*Russia the terrorist slayer*,” the third information tactic identified in Russian IW.

Table 10. Cluster 3: “Russia + DESTROYED / KILLED + militants / terrorists”

#	Left context	Keyword in context	Right context
1	Russian #AirForce destroyed Military Police #ISIL headquarters in Uqayrbat city. About 20	militants	were killed and 1 vehicle was de-destroyed .
2	Russian aviation destroyed the last two tanks of the #HTS	terrorists	in the Jarjanaz area. #Syria
3	#Russian_Air_Force destroyed a convoy with ammunition and food for #ISIL	#terrorists	
4	Russian and Syrian aviation destroyed 3 pickups with a large-caliber machine gun and one bus as well as more than 50	militants	were killed
5	#Russian air defense systems in Syria shot down two	#terrorist’s	#drones

Information Tactic 4: Russia the Humanitarian

Finally, we examine the concordance lines containing **people,* *civilian,** and **refugee** filtered for the context of *Russia*. We found that the word *humanitarian*, ranked 13th on the list of keywords, occurs in the tweets analyzed in Table 11. A further search for *humanitarian* has revealed that it collocates, i.e., occurs most typically, with the words *aid* (n=131), *action* (n=65), *corridor* (n=53), *convoy* (n=46), and *situation* (n=46). The verbs used most typically to describe Russia’s humanitarian action are *provided* and *delivered*, construed as factual statements. Place names (e.g., *Um al-Izam in #Homs, in #Aleppo province*) included in each tweet signal how far Russian assistance spreads. The co-patterning of these resources forms the fourth information tactic identified in IW. We named this information tactic that serves to highlight Russia’s claim of moral superiority “*Russia the humanitarian*.”

Table 11. Cluster 4: “Russia + PROVIDES + humanitarian aid + to civilians / refugees”

#	Left context	Keyword in context	Right context
1	The Russian military provided humanitarian aid to the	people	of Um al-Izam in #Homs. #Syria
2	#Russian soldiers gave humanitarian aid to	civilians	in #Aleppo province
3	The #Russian Federation has fully fulfilled its obligations to organize the delivery of #UN humanitarian aid to the #Rukban	#refugee	camp
4	#Russia delivered humanitarian aid to the Syrian	people	in the city of Ira in the province of Essaouida
5	#Russia organized humanitarian corridors for 13 thousand of Syrian	#refugees	to leave the fighting zone in #EasternG-houta

The four information tactics presented above are summarized in Table 12. Russia’s negative portrayal of the US as *terrorist recruiter* and *civilian killer* foreground the condemnation and moral inferiority of the US for terrorist recruitment and its alleged human rights abuses, portraying it as a destabilizing power in Syria. In contrast, Russia’s positive portrayal of its own involvement and actions as *terrorist slayer* and *humanitarian* functions to foreground both admiration of Russian military strength and capability and praise of its moral superiority for its humanitarian interventions, portraying Russia as a stabilizing power in Syria.

Table 12. Key information tactics and their linguistic features in Russian information warfare

Information tactic		Recurring linguistic pattern
US	terrorist recruiter	The US + RECRUITS / TRAINS + militants / terrorists
	civilian killer	the US + KILLED + x number of + civilians
Russia	terrorist slayer	Russia + DESTROYS / KILLS + militants / terrorists
	humanitarian	Russia + PROVIDES + humanitarian aid + civilians / refugees

Comparing information tactics to kinetic operations

To gain a fuller perspective on the deployment of information tactics in relation to Russia’s use of force, we compare the results of the concordance analyses to the open-source conflict data on Russian military operations.⁵² Several patterns emerge. Figure 1 visualizes temporal variation across Russian military actions targeting civilians, groups widely designated as terrorists and other armed rebel and opposition groups.⁵³ While kinetic operations against civilian and rebel targets ramped up between mid-2017 and mid-2018, as illustrated in Figure 1, Russian information warfare emphasized information tactics 1 and 2 (Figure 2) to manufacture alternate versions of events in which Russian operations were prolifically killing terrorists and supplying humanitarian aid. The spike in the latter tactic lags behind the former and appears to respond to the spike in increased civilian targeting in Figure 1—a *reactive* tactic reminiscent of what the NATO Strategic Communications Centre of Excellence refers to as Russia’s “fog of falsehood.”⁵⁴ During a lull in Russian kinetic activity encompassing the period between Russia’s Idlib demilitarization deal with Turkey in September 2018, and the agreement’s ultimate collapse in May 2019 (Figure 1), information tactics shifted strongly to those framing the US-led coalition as *recruiting terrorists* while simultaneously *killing civilians* (Figure 3).⁵⁵ As Russian military operations began to build up in early 2019, we again see a marked increase of the information tactics *Russia the terrorist slayer* and *Russia the humanitarian*, followed by a dramatic spike in *America the terrorist recruiter* and *America the civilian killer* as the campaign progressed. Finally, as kinetic operations wound down in the latter half of 2020, so too did the corresponding information campaign.

Figure 1. Variation in Russian military targets between 2017 and 2020

**Figure 2. Russian information tactics 1 and 2 over time:
*Russia the terrorist slayer and Russia the humanitarian***

Figure 3. Russian information tactics 3 and 4 over time:
America the terrorist recruiter and America the civilian killer

Discussion

This article set out to examine how Russia framed its own involvement and actions in the Syrian civil war in comparison to those of the international coalition, led by the US. Since Russian state and social media claimed that Russia's mission in Syria was to fight "international terrorism," we sought to unpack Russia's covert Twitter campaign surrounding the Syrian civil war between 2016 and 2020. The detailed corpus linguistic analyses presented above helped reveal the Russian information tactics used to discredit the US and its allies while lauding Russia's efforts in the Syrian civil war. Comparing the weaponization of information with on-the-ground conflict data, we found that the versions of reality communicated by these four information tactics formed a more permissive environment for Russia to accomplish military objectives that were actually in direct contrast with its framing of events. At the same time, Russia's disinformation campaign in Syria continued to advance its larger geopolitical objectives in the information space, such as undermining the influence of the West and projecting itself as a global superpower. The information tactics most closely tied to Russian military objectives are *terrorist slayer* and *humanitarian*, each contributing to the strategic narrative that Russia was in Syria to fight international terrorism. Thus, tweets associated with such information tactics serve to justify Russian involvement, creating the perception that their offensives focus exclusively, and very successfully, on vanquishing ISIS and caring for displaced and injured civilians.

Despite overt strategic communication portraying intervention as a fight against international terrorism, Russian military activity directly targeting ISIS and other terrorist groups remained minimal throughout the period of analysis. In fact, Russian overt

communication (e.g., by Putin or the Ministries of Foreign Affairs and Defense) continually reported air strikes against terrorist targets despite a pattern of discrepancies between claimed target locations and the locations confirmed by independent, open-source analysis, the majority of which had no known connection to ISIS or international terrorism.⁵⁶ Indeed, the Atlantic Council's Digital Forensics Lab concludes that Russian bombing had very little effect on ISIS or the al-Nusra Front and instead served mostly to weaken US-backed opposition and rebel groups, directly enabling ISIS to gain ground and the Assad regime to reclaim territory in Syria.⁵⁷

To summarize, the covert Twitter network appears to favor the *terrorist slayer* and *humanitarian* tactics during initial phases of a kinetic campaign, before rather overwhelmingly turning to *terrorist recruiter* and *civilian killer*. This is significant for the study of IW because Russian information tactics did not simply *prepare* the terrain for their military operations; it *created* the terrain—seeding the information space with justifications enabling physical intervention, while proceeding to undermine any information advantage of the international coalition. In its geopolitical power play and struggle to reclaim its position as a significant military and diplomatic force, Russia's strategic disinformation centers around information tactics that are delivered as factual assertions beyond debate, as real events on the ground. As Lev Topor and Alexander Tabachnik argue, Russian information operations are offensive rather than defensive.⁵⁸ Indeed, our findings underscore the notion that Russian offensives in the physical world are part and parcel to those in the information space.

While the Kremlin consistently denied the allegations of human rights abuses, Russian offensives repeatedly used illegal cluster munitions and targeted civilian objects, including hospitals and aid facilities, civilian homes, mosques, and schools.⁵⁹ These airstrikes and cluster bomb attacks resulted in an estimated 4,000 to 6,000 civilian deaths in Syria between 2015 and 2020 and likely constitute war crimes.⁶⁰ Contrary to Kremlin narratives of “helping civilians,” Russian and Assad forces’ military tactics resulted in the displacement of people in areas held by opposition forces, creating an international refugee crisis.⁶¹

Syria is not the first place the Kremlin has used virtually manufactured realities to justify the use of physical force, nor is it insignificant that a humanitarian theme runs through its framing of military interventions in Georgia, Ukraine, and Syria.⁶² While the conflicts in Georgia and Ukraine (2014) may be where Russia developed and tested its hybrid warfare for use in its “near abroad,” Syria presents a different case. One Russia expert, Troy Bouffard, referred in a recent keynote to Syria as a “combat training exercise center” for updating its military capabilities debuted in Ukraine.⁶³ Our analysis suggests this characterization may also include Russia's IW capabilities, which, this time were deployed alongside military operations in the Russian “far abroad” and in direct confrontation with an American-led operation.

Concluding Remarks

Our objective in conducting this analysis was to provide actionable insight into

how Russian information warfare framed Russian and American coalition involvement in the Syrian civil war, with an emphasis on how this framing aligned with strategic objectives and events on the ground. At the time of writing this article, the *New York Times* broke the news in a series of articles that the Bakhuz airstrike by the US killed dozens of civilians, including women and children.⁶⁴ Independent reporting also estimates that American coalition offensives resulted in 8,000 to 13,000 civilian deaths across Syria and Iraq.⁶⁵ The purpose of this article is not to absolve the US and its allies of responsibility for its humanitarian record in Syria, nor is it to portray Russia as the sole cause of civilian death. Any alleged infringement upon the rule of distinction between civilians and combatants is to be considered first a human tragedy and second a possible violation of customary international humanitarian law, irrespective of the perpetrator.⁶⁶ What we found in our analysis was a strategic disinformation campaign realized by discrete information tactics presenting alternative versions of events as indisputable facts. These virtual realities justified military operations claiming to target terrorism and to provide aid, while mostly ignoring ISIS and instead targeting Assad's opponents, including civilians and civilian objects. Meanwhile, these information tactics ascribed blame for civilian casualties entirely to the US and its allies. It is therefore appropriate to accurately cite Russia's humanitarian impact in this article not only because their disinformation campaign directly supported physical operations resulting in civilian death and displacement, but also because the topic of civilian death and displacement was itself weaponized to manipulate international perceptions of events on the ground.

In addition to shaping the Syrian operational environment, information warfare continued to advance overarching geopolitical objectives emblematic of Russian IW strategy—namely undermining the influence of the West and positioning itself as a global superpower.⁶⁷ We consider framing the US as a *terrorist recruiter* and *civilian killer* as belonging to a *declining West* strategic narrative family, while Russia's portrayal as the *terrorist slayer* and *humanitarian* advances the strategic narrative that Russia is a powerful and ethical alternative to Western influence. This conclusion aligns with the German Marshall Fund's observation that Russian information warfare is not so much guided by any single event, as by overarching narratives associated with long-term objectives.⁶⁸ In other words, covert information tactics in Syria serve not only to justify the use of force against Assad's perceived opponents and undermine America's position in the Syrian information space, but also to advance Russia's image as a superpower while damaging the global influence of the West. Further emphasizing the strategic import of these contrasting covert information tactics, a recent report from NATO's Strategic Communications Centre of Excellence found that overt communication by state-backed media (e.g., *Russia Today* and *Sputnik*) also framed Russian involvement in Syria by contrasting Russia's provision of humanitarian aid with America's collusion with terrorists, significantly amplifying the reach of these covertly seeded narratives.⁶⁹

Just as the *defending Russian diaspora* narrative outlived its deployment in Georgia and has since been observed in disinformation campaigns in Ukraine and across the former

Soviet “near abroad,” variations of the information tactics we identify in the Syrian “combat training exercise center” may well appear and indicate future physical intervention in other international contexts. The analytical framework we demonstrate enables us to identify the ways in which the language of individual messages clusters into narrative lines of effort based upon the repeated framing of collectivized and human entities (e.g., *America + trains + terrorists*), signaling the potential for future research efforts to recognize and detect known tactics as they are used in different operational environments. This process can in turn help researchers to identify broader strategic narratives (e.g., *declining West*) and information objectives (e.g., undermining American influence) in an ecosystem intentionally polluted by diverse and mutually contradicting articles of information.

Shortly before this article was finalized and submitted, Russia commenced an invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022. Much as Russian military intervention in Syria was ushered in with the tactical use of *humanitarian* and *terrorist slayer* narratives to justify the use of force, Russian strategic communication characterized its invasion of Ukraine as a “special military operation” whose objective was the “demilitarization and denazification of Ukraine” and to “defend people who for eight years are suffering persecution and genocide by the Kyiv regime.”⁷⁰ This justification was seeded by weeks of false flag narratives, information tactics framing the US, NATO, and the Ukrainian government as aggressors bent on encircling Russia and committing atrocities, including terrorist attacks and genocide against Russian-speaking populations in Ukraine.⁷¹ Since the invasion began, we continue to witness an unyielding barrage of Russian disinformation framing Ukraine and NATO as aggressive, morally corrupt actors. This disinformation includes claims that Ukrainian leadership is infested with neo-Nazis and drug addicts, that Ukrainian and American governments have collaborated to develop biological weapons for use against Russia, and that the Russian military is targeting radicals and Nazis while actually attacking civilian objects such as maternity hospitals.⁷² The discrepancy between claimed extremist targets and real, often civilian targets is, of course, tragically familiar.

A detailed analysis of Russian disinformation during its invasion of Ukraine is needed to fully break down the anatomy of information tactics in the Ukrainian theatre, however observing the developments in real-time is enough to suggest several similarities between their campaigns in Syria and Ukraine. While returning to *defending Russian diaspora* narratives, the Russian information offensive against Ukraine continues to hinge upon the diametrically opposed symbols of innocent civilians and violent extremists, be they terrorists or neo-Nazis. On one side of this hinge, Russia protects civilians and destroys extremists, while on the other, its adversaries commit unspeakable atrocities and collude with extremists. The *declining West* and *Russian superpower* strategic narratives are once again being leveraged in the Ukrainian conflict. The ebbs, flows, and narrative adaptations of this latest Russian information war will doubtlessly inform and be informed by as yet unknown developments on the ground. The present Ukrainian conflict is the latest and most powerful reminder of just how interconnected Russian IW and their kinetic operations really are.

In sum, strategic disinformation positioned Russia as the most significant actor in the fight against international terrorism, a stabilizing presence in the region with the most powerful military. Information objectives in this context are not concerned with accuracy, credibility, trust, or even persuasion but are focused instead on creating “an exaggerated view of Russia’s economic and military power.”⁷³ This resonates with findings of previous research on public perceptions of Russia in its “far abroad,” especially in Central and Eastern Europe, where Russia has been successful in “inflating” its authoritarian superpower image.⁷⁴ Disinformation analysis should therefore accordingly orient its methodological frameworks to address how IW targets liberal democratic society above all else. In keeping with this, our analysis treats weaponized information tactics as 1) possessing a *narrative*, because they seek to resonate with ideologies, theories, and beliefs, and “points the way to future actions,” and 2) *strategic*, because they seek advantage by targeting an audience’s cognitive vulnerabilities with premises they are predisposed to accept.⁷⁵ Future research thus needs to study from a social cybersecurity perspective the reach, distribution, and impact of disinformation campaigns on targeted audiences, and the extent to which they act as a threat multiplier in polarizing societies.

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